

TYPES OF TEACHING ENGLISH MATERIALS FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

Yaqubova Nigora Ibrohimjon qizi

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences
Faculty of History and Philology
Teacher of the Department of
Foreign Language and Literature

Abstract. This article deals with the importance of learning English for school-aged children. It also examines the development of pupils' ability to get engaged the lesson and it devotes the methods of teaching English to primary school children.

Key words: children of school age, English language, language, pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods

Эта статья о важности изучения английского языка для детей школьного возраста, его важности сегодня и в основном охватывает методы преподавания английского языка детям дошкольного возраста.

Ключевые слова: дети школьного возраста, английский язык, язык, педагогические технологии, интерактив, инновационные методы.

Introduction

Language is the main means of communication, without which it is difficult to imagine the existence and development of human society. Today, knowledge of foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. A new stage, a new era has begun in the teaching of foreign languages in our country.

The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools is required in the process of teaching foreign language classes. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the new recommendations for foreign language teaching and evaluation of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers (CEFR). In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped

with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into 4 aspects (reading, writing, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them.

Teaching children is a very difficult issue that requires a completely different methodological approach than schoolchildren and adults. If an adult speaks a foreign language, it does not mean that he can teach others. When faced with methodologically inefficient lessons, pupils can long-term feel aversion towards the foreign language and lose confidence in their abilities. Therefore, it requires to work mostly experienced professionals with young learners children.

The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 7-8-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of learning a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest.

Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible. The following methods can be used to teach children English in a meaningful and interesting way: - through songs and poems, to teach words and phrases that are difficult to explain or remember, and have no meaning.

For example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it. - games related to mental and physical activities; - cartoons; While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters.

This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language. - role play, the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: one student

shows a dog howling, a cat meowing, another student can show which animal these sounds are. - subject environment; If the teacher can create that environment depending on the subject, the children will learn the language better. For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc. On the topic of traveling, the teacher organizes a trip, information about the importance of traveling (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA) will give. This situation strengthens the students' vocabulary, language abilities, and expands their worldview.

Children start learning foreign languages from the first grade of secondary school. On the one hand, this is a great opportunity to get knowledge at least at the B1 level before graduation, on the other hand, it adds questions to teachers. Because it is not easy to choose the right teaching method to achieve good results.

It consists of learning the rules of English grammar in one or two lessons with explanations and strengthening them with written or oral exercises. The teacher actively works with children, chooses different types of activities: writing, reading, repeating. However, the disadvantage is that due to the large number of children, it is not always possible to accurately check the level of success of the material studied. The main idea is to immerse children in the language environment and traditional life of the country. The following interactive methods are included in teaching English in primary school:

- reading children's fiction and working with them;
- reading books in two or more languages,
- watching cartoons,
- active work in pairs and mini-groups;
- studying real life situations in a foreign language;
- a large amount of speaking practice.

Suggestion and conclusions: When teaching a foreign language to children of preschool age, it is necessary to take into account the unique characteristics of children. For example, children often memorize mechanically rather than

understanding the content. Therefore, in teaching foreign language to children of primary school pupils, it is necessary to effectively use play-education without overstressing them.

Lessons should be organized taking into account the child's interests and age characteristics. Information should be neither too simple nor too heavy. In both cases, the child's interest in learning the language may fade. The following methods should be used effectively when teaching a foreign language to young learners:

1. Using visual materials to teach new words. Live display of the words being learned in the process, if there is a word related to the object: pen-pencil (the pen is shown)
2. Teaching songs and poems with actions. Teaching songs and rhymes with action helps children make logical connections between words and actions, facilitating memorization skills.
3. Memorizing the alphabet of a foreign language in the form of a song with various actions. Rather than simply memorizing the alphabet through words, this method is also interesting for the child, and when it is said to the accompaniment, it creates a cheerful mood.
4. Performing various physical exercises accompanied by songs in a foreign language. When using different physical moments to record children's fatigue during the training, the use of foreign language words also has a positive result in language learning.

As we all know, the opportunities to learn a foreign language from preschool age are truly incomparable. As an example, we use K.D. We can quote these writings of Ushenisky. "A child learns in a few months what we cannot learn in a few years. From this idea, we can understand that children should be introduced to foreign languages from preschool age. Mechanical memorization of children and broadening their spiritual world view will help them to learn languages. arouses interest. Game activity arouses more interest in children.

Currently, higher demands are placed on the speech development of preschool children. Meeting these demands requires new research on speech development. Thus, at the current stage of the science of pedagogy, there are conflicts between the requirements for the development of preschool children's speech and these requirements. Based on the above considerations, we decided to highlight the theoretical and methodical methods that will serve as a basis for the development of effective ways and tools for the development of preschool children's speech in this article.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Puchkova, Yu. Ya. Games in English lessons: Method. allowance. M.: AST Publishing House LLC, 2005. - 78 p
2. Johnson, K. E. The Sociocultural Turn and Its Challenges for Second Language Teacher Education. // TESOL Quarterly., – London., 2006.
3. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. – London., 2001.
4. Passov E. I. General method of foreign exchange training. - Moscow., 1985.
5. Mehri Norova. Application of lexical unit and lexical transformation in translation.
6. <https://baxtiyor.uz/o-zbekistonda-chet-tillarini-o-qitish-muammolari-ular-qanchalik-jiddiy/>
7. Bobojonova, S. (2022). The analysis of the educational discourse and speech of the participants of the activity.
8. Gulfura, T., Bobojonova, S., Shakhnoza, A., Komila, S., & Doniyor, A. (2019). The role of task based learning in teaching english.
7. Esonovna, A. S. (2023). Substitution of Latin and Greek Morphemes in Words in Medical Terminology. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 4(2), 32-34. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9P4FD>
8. Esonovna, A. S. (2020). Linguistic features of Latin and Greek synonymous morphemes in the lexical system of the french language. *International scientific review*, (LXXII), 47-48.